

Overview of Juvenile Delinquency in Nigeria Schools: Theoretical Approaches and Psychotherapeutic Interventions

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Abstract

Contemporary world has seen increase in the rate of offences and crimes committed by juveniles which are a very serious problem in Nigeria, particularly, as these juveniles are the future of their respective communities. Most sensitively, more and more children are moving towards the pathway of crime to lead their lives. Various factors are responsible for these antisocial behaviours. This paper is therefore tempted to present causal factors of juvenile delinquency such as; family background, financial situation, biogenic and psychogenic problems, social discrimination, amoral issues, parenting style, self-concept, peer group, environment, lawlessness and the media. It also discussed some theories of delinquency and further highlighted probable solutions to juvenile delinquency such as individual and group counselling, family counselling, modeling, rational emotive therapy and other psychotherapeutic approaches. The paper proffered conclusion and recommendations such as; involvement of psychotherapists in schools, provision and enforcement of effective rules and regulations, periodic orientation of new students and teachers in schools, effective parenting, regular Parents Teachers Association (PTA), vocational training for skills acquisition, adequate provision of educational needs of children and teachers, supervision and monitoring of children's behaviour and introduction of motivation award for good behaviour. These strategies are to prevent or avert delinquent manifestations and capable of bringing about positive changes in character modification among children.

Keywords: Juvenile, Delinquency, Theoretical approaches, Psychotherapeutic solution, Manifestations

Introduction

Delinquency is an antisocial act by children and a proportion of adult criminals have a background of early delinquency. Farrington (2004) described delinquency as crimes committed by young people which range from littering to murder. The trend in the study of juvenile delinquency is the concern of every individual in Nigerian society because it has moved gradually from the focus on physical and psychological composition of the individual to the influence of the social structure on an individual. This touches the whole society; the government, the judiciary, family, school, teachers, psychologists, counsellors and other

stakeholders. The claim that delinquent behaviours arise from entirely different situations has led studies beyond that of Cesare Lombroso, (1835 – 1909), ascribed as the Father of Modern Criminology, who claimed that physical defects such as inability, ugliness etc are crucial in the explanation of delinquency. Modern psychologists claim that delinquent behaviour is an out trust of unsocialized, original animal impulses. Sociologists however, claim that deviant behaviour as well as normal behaviour is a product of social environment such as the family, school, peer group and other agents (Tayo, 2017).

The environment where the child lives has much to do with his behaviour as

Tayo (2017) confirmed this assumption when he said that, a community with a high crime rate, cannot but expose its adolescents to criminal activities since they have to copy models who are into criminality. He also identified predictors of delinquency to include conflict with authority, minor covert acts followed by property damage, minor aggression followed by fighting and violence. More signs of delinquency (Tayo, 2007). According to Loeber and Farrington (2001), they also included authority conflict. This has to do with show of stubbornness before the age of twelve. There is convert behaviour which include minor convert acts; such as lying, leading gradually to more serious delinquency. Lastly, is the exhibition of overt behaviour which includes aggression followed by fighting and violence.

The observed increase in the incidence of delinquency among our secondary school adolescents towards constituted authority could be attributed to more social forces, which are traceable to factors such as; changes in parenting styles, teacher-student relationship, social media or technological advancement. For example, despite the fact that parents play very important roles in children's development, it is observed that most parents today hardly have the time to look after their children. This could be resulting from the fact that most women now go to work outside the home to earn money in order to support the family. Thus, children are left in the hands of house helps or dropped at the crèche, where not much attention is given to them. The implication is that most of the children grow up lacking proper supervision, having neither moral nor spiritual guidance. Roth and Brooks – Gunn (2000) explained that though adolescents are moving towards independence, yet we should not deny them of the need to stay connected with their parents. Along this same line, the longitudinal study on the Adolescent

Health of the Council of Economic Advisors (AHCEA) (2000), found that more than 12,000 adolescents who did not eat dinner with their parents for five or more days a week, had dramatically higher rates of smoking, drinking, engaging in marijuana use, getting into fighting and initiation into sexual activities. In another study by Mounts (2002) parents who played an active role in monitoring and guiding their adolescents' development, were found with adolescents who had positive peer relations and lower drug use, than parents who had less active roles.

More studies by Tayo (2012), showed that there are increasing number of children growing up in divorced or separated families. This implies that there are far more elementary and secondary school children living in step families. Hetherington & Kelly (2002), found that children in step families show more adjustment problems than those in non-divorced families, and are liable to adjustment problems in academic work and also psychologically show low self-esteem. Competent adolescents' development most likely occurs when they have parents who show them warmth and mutual respect; have interest in their lives, and display constructive ways in dealing with their problems or conflicts. Schools and teachers have important roles to play for them all for the all – round development of their student. Tayo (2012) stressed teachers' powerful influence on the school adolescents particularly as role models while Buzzelli and Johnston (2018s) view moral perspectives on teacher's education to include; redefining teacher – student relationship, decontextualizing curse methods and content knowledge.

Tayo (2017) while reflecting on the effective performance of teacher's duties was not happy that recently, there had been large number of students per class. Also, he noted too that, there had been shortage in the number of teachers. This according to Tayo (2017), has a lot of implications for

quality control in classroom teaching, as it could encourage students' unrest, and their involvement in diverse negative behaviours such as; examination malpractice, fighting, truancy and others. Again, another disheartening situation that could dampen the morale of teachers is the observation made by Pota (2015), which showed that there had been drastic decline in the respect for teachers internationally. Pota noted that teachers often face intimidation even from parents of their students. Parents increasingly fail to back the authority of teachers for their wards or children. There is also lack of incentives to teachers from the government. It is very sad that even now, at the 21st century, teachers are still wallowing in much poverty, as their salaries for months are often not paid. This could further explain the care-free attitudes of teachers to their duties; and why incessant strike actions have always been the order of the day, which all affect children's character.

It is a general belief that many youngsters are initiated into smoking, drinking, bullying and other anti-social or delinquent behaviours through the social media. According to Kariku (2016), the teens are exposed to everything through the social media. He felt that no matter how hard parents try to protect the adolescents from negative news, it seems to be impossible. DeAngelis (2007) trying to link media violence to real-life violent behaviours stated that there is no doubt, children, like adults are equally exposed to a tremendous amount of violence through the media. It could be added here that, it is not only in the industrialized societies alone, as being expressed by the preceding scholars, that people spend more of their leisure time with electronic media than any other activity but it also happens in developing countries such as Nigeria. This paper is therefore tempted to discuss some causal factors of juvenile delinquency and to proffer probable solutions to these antisocial behaviours so as to prevent and

remolds the character of Nigerian youth as effective citizens.

Concepts of Delinquency, Juvenile and Adolescence

The word 'delinquent', is used to refer to children committing offences against the law, but it also includes those children committing crimes of various sorts or manifesting forms of abnormalities in their behaviour, especially adolescents, which may or may not amount to offence punishable by law (Mukherjee, 2002). The period of adolescence is a period of crises, and the psychology of adolescents will be considered to unfold the causal factors of such behaviour.

According to Niyi (2015), there is no universal definition of a juvenile or delinquency. The laws of different nations stipulate different age brackets for the juveniles. Juveniles' delinquency refers to the violation of the criminal codes, regulating the behaviour of young persons in the society. Besides, the concept of a juvenile is sometimes used interchangeably with other concepts like a child, an adolescent and a youth. However, the law is usually more specific in its definition of a child or juvenile or youth.

The Children and Young Persons Act (CYPA) according to Niyi (2015), defines a child as a person under the age of fourteen years. Also, the law defines a young person as a person who has attained the age of fourteen years. The law however, did not define a juvenile. However, other indicators in the law show that the term refers to a person under the age of seventeen years. Juvenile delinquency broadly defined, refers to any act in violation of criminal law, committed by a person defined under law as juvenile, which if that offence has been committed by an adult will be treated as crimes or criminal conduct. In addition to conducts which constitute delinquency for the juvenile but crime for the adults, there are other behaviours that do not constitute crime for adult which are defined as delinquency,

when manifested by children and young persons.

The above behaviours are referred to as 'status offences', because of the status of the young persons. Status offence under juvenile delinquency laws of different countries include diverse behaviours such as: lying, cruelty, bullying, running away from home, smoking, drinking alcohol in public, moving with criminals and prostitute, examination malpractices, noisemaking, fighting, vandalism, use of foul language, stealing, cheating, gambling, truancy, stubbornness, untidiness, sexual harassment, mob action, littering, carrying of harmful or dangerous weapons and other aggressive behaviours. It is a condition of drift, maladjustment, pathology, disturbance, moral depravity and unruly behaviour. (Niyi, 2015). The definition, manifestations and control of juvenile delinquency are influenced by a configuration of historical, political, social and economic conditions. No doubt, the vague definition of delinquency leads to wide discretionary and discriminatory powers on the part of law enforcement officer and juvenile administrators. Over the past ten years, the members of juvenile court cases have doubled in West Africa (George, 2007). According to UNICEF (2008), those countries and communities that were considered safe and peaceful are being supplanted by deep anxiety and terrorism as increasing number of young Nigerians are getting more involved in criminality. According to Abubakar (2018), Because of the alarming rate of juvenile delinquency in our country today. Governments, parents, guidance, sponsors, teachers, moralist, and well-meaning Nigerians have all picked interest on its adverse effects in society. Also, the increasing wave of juvenile delinquency in our country place lives properties and future of our youth at stake. For example in 1989 record of crime as reported by Lagos state police command revealed that 13,782 out of 26, 259 youths between the ages of

thirteen (13) and twenty one (21) were responsible for crimes committed this year.

Similar report also indicated that in the same year (1989) out of 43,000 prisoners serving in various Nigerian prisons, over 23,000 of them were aged between the ages of thirteen (13) and twenty-five (25) years. Amajionwu (1974) also studied 901 delinquents who indicated 9670 offences committed by them. He reported that between 1971 and 1973, delinquency rate had increased by 87.3% and that more offences were discovered among delinquent children in various cities. Denga (1981), Ikeme and Emodi (1987) in their findings reported increase in incidences of juvenile delinquency in Nigeria. Judging from biogenic theory that says that physical structure or deformation determines one's ability or inability to indulge in criminal offences, if children with disabilities are provided with special education programmes to exercise equal right, they will be equal to the task.

The individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) identified fourteen categories of students with special needs including; autism, spectrum disorders, deaf-blindness, deafness, developmental delay, emotion disturbance, hearing impairment, mental retardation, multiple disabilities, orthopedic impairment, other health impairment, specific learning disability, speech impairment, traumatic brain injury and visual impairment including blindness. These impairments or deprivations make the children unable to cope with the normal school class organization and teaching methods. (F.R.N, 2004). At the World conference on Special Needs Education in Jomtein, Thailand in 1990 they focused on integration initiatives and equity issues for all including those with special needs. In 1994, another World conference on Special Needs Education was organized by the United Education, Scientific, Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in which Nigeria was a signatory, reaffirmed its commitment to

Education For All (EFA) (UNESCO 1994). Another World Conference was organized by UNESCO in the Dakar Framework for Action to reaffirm Education For All. Added to this was the world Conference on Special Education which took place in Salamanca, Spain in 1994 to give Filip to Inclusive Education (IE). (UNESCO, 1994).

Eno (2000) and Nwazuoke (2000) in their submissions in respect of the workability of special education or inclusive education in Nigeria, children with disabilities are still at disadvantage and educating all the disabilities is still a long hurdle. For instance, parents are not cooperating or helping their disabled children to be registered in formal schools rather than begging, lack of accurate and up to date data of the exceptional children in Nigeria; lack of qualified special teachers, inability to transport children with disabilities to schools particularly from poor families; lack of provision of teaching and learning materials such as computer, voice calculator, Braille machines and wheelchairs, graphic models, mental health centers and guidance clinics and most importantly, the possibility of getting these children with disabilities gainfully employed. Since these categories of children are not yet been catered for by parents and the government, there is hardly any reliable research findings to testify that physical, mental or emotional disability is related to juvenile delinquency in Nigeria. Therefore, this paper positions itself based on research findings of other countries.

Meadows (2007) Harris (2009) in their national longitudinal survey and school-based research in the United States discovered that there is relationship between children with disabilities and delinquency. Krieger (2004) reported in his investigation that children with disabilities participated in gang initiation and property crime, while other researchers added that some children with disabilities were at risk of reliant behaviour problems of selling

drugs, weapon use, and having sex while under the influence of substance, and are more likely to run away from school than those without disabilities. Corrie and Dennis (2012) in Caroline, Virginia and other towns in the United State studied of 7,232, children with disabilities in relation to delinquency, including those with learning disability, chronic health, condition, sensory condition, physical disability, multiple disabilities. In the finding, 38% of these disabled children were one time or the other involved in stealing, destruction of property (32.1%), attacking someone (25.2%), running away from home, (15.5%), gang membership (10.1%), diverse stealing (10.8), other property incarceration, (12.9%). Males comprise 50.7% of the full sample while females are 49.3%.

Theories and Causes of Juvenile Delinquency

The psychologists, psychiatrists, lawyers, philosophers and sociologists have embarked on various studies to understand criminal behaviour and have put forward many theories regarding this. Many opinions, reasons and suggestions related to the cause of delinquency have been printed in various sources, but they have hardly ever been incorporated. Most of the theories regarding delinquency and crime suggest that they cannot be explained in terms of one single informal factor (Stewart, 2005).

Generally, there are three major views such as:

- A. Biogenic theory
- B. Psychogenic theory
- C. Sociogenic theory

A. Biogenic Theory

Biogenic theory is based upon the conception that the natural body structure of offenders or criminals is generally different from normal human beings and therefore a biological phenomenon, whose criminal tendency originates from his physical characters (Ceases Lambroso (1835-1909), regarded as the founder of

biogenic theory. He declared that a criminal originated from atavistic phenomenon and that somatological characteristics of criminals resemble those of primitive men. According to him, a typical criminal has certain physical characteristics as type of forehead, hairy body, red eyes, ear deformation, receding chin, big and protruding jaws, and an extreme sensitivity or non-sensitivity to pain. He was serving as physician in the army where he observed that troublesome soldiers had certain different physical characteristics which were missing in other soldiers (Niyi, 2015 and Tayo, 2017).

The Federal Government of Nigeria, being sensitive of caring for children with special needs or children with disabilities, introduced in its policy on education, the education of special need people since 1977, built special schools for physically challenged, and special colleges where many special teachers were trained. Compulsory, free, Universal Basic Education was inaugurated in 1999 by the government and passed into law as the 'The Universal Basic Education Law? (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2004).

B. Environmental Factor

Children's manifestations of behaviour attributes depend on the environment (nurture) from where these children emanate or where they live with their parents, guardians or caretakers. Kreager (2004) asserted that the family background has the greatest influence on the offensive behaviour of juveniles, particularly if they find the parents indulging in any antisocial behaviour, they can imitate them (cases of criminal parents, family instability, crisis in broken home or heredity). It is worse if the parents refuse to correct juvenile delinquents, they are likely to indulge or perpetrate in such similar or different offences. Niyi (2015) and Kariku (2017) reported that some juveniles use means of transport possessed by family or peers to indulge in criminal offences. They further explained that constant cultural

conflicts among communities could be further practiced by new generations such as those happening in Nigeria, the Eskimos, Indo-Pakistani crisis since 1947. These clashes could be land dispute, social or economic crisis. Also, family size and type of family, parent – children relationship, socio-economic condition of family, peer group, nature of school, neighborhood relationship, accessibility to media, are causal factors of delinquent acts.

C. Physiological and Personal

The school plays a significant role for the growth and development of the child. It is the place children have the closest friends over the maximum period of time. If a school is staffed with cruel teachers who punish unjustifiably, children are likely to imitate these teachers or even senior students will indulge in bullying the younger ones. Pilfering, stealing, snatching, drug addiction, gangsterism, sexual molestation or harassment, vandalism and demonstration are some of the offences practiced and learnt in schools. (Kreager, 2004, Meadows, 2007; Harris, 2009, Carrie and Dennis, 2012). Children practice delinquent acts where environments are in the state of anomie. Merton's theory of anomie explains that lawless children satisfy themselves through unlawful means. (Kreager, 2004; Meadow, 2007; Harns, 2009, Carrie and Dennis, 2012).

Psychological Implications of Juvenile Delinquency

Cognitive structural view point of Piaget and Kohlberg, written by Kay (1970) comes to mind in the cognitive development of the child. According to Piaget, as stated by Kay, the child develops morality in four stages including egocentric, the authoritarian, the reciprocal and the equity. In the egocentric stage (2-5 years), the child's moral reasoning has no consideration for others rather than themselves. The child's intent is pleurability and it does not matter whether others suffer or are injured while he gains his desires. The authoritarian stage

(5-8 years) makes children to judge morality in absolute terms. Since parents or authorities say that stealing is bad, if a child steals under any circumstance, he must be punished. Obedience rules show good behaviour while disobedience shows bad behaviour. Since actions are not numbered, children may be indulging in certain offensive act which they think it is not offensive. The reciprocal stage (8-11 years) is where children begin to realize that rules are not absolute or natural but are made by society and can be changed. It is based on “do to others what you want others to do to you”. The equity stage (8-10 years) is when children reason morally beyond legalistic considerations. A child may support his brother who has stolen food without permission of the mother. If the mother scorns the brother, the junior child can support the brother that the brother needed more food because he was not satisfied and therefore feels the action is justifiable and to the mother, it is an offence. Thus, the theory is about a high moral level of reasoning does not necessarily go with a high moral level of behaviour. The limitation of this theory is that adolescent with severe delinquency may still be “matching time” at the egocentric stage by gratifying his desires without taking into consideration how it affects others. He may use hard object to hit the screen of a television in the mood of playing.

Social learning according to Edward (2017), views morality as a socially learnt behaviour acquired through instruction, modelling and imitation and facilitated and maintained by reinforcement or rewards. These instructions, orders, directives, are received from significant others, teachers, peers, priests and community leaders. Thus, the juvenile misbehaves because he has not been morally brought up either by home, school or environment. This theory believes that there are individual juvenile delinquents who are quite aware of the laid down rules

and yet flout the rules and goes into misbehave.

Behavioural theory: Behavioural theory or moral behaviour according to Edward (2017) was best formulated by Eysenck in 1947. According to Eysenck, the socialization of a child is determined by personality of the child and the environment. The environment includes the home, the school, the religious institutions, peer group and the community. To Eysenck, a person may be extroverted, introverted or ambiverted. In addition, he may either be stable, somewhat stable or unstable in how he reacts emotionally. It could be heredity from parents. Thus, one has to interact with the environment before one can shape his or her personality. These include the type of parental child rearing model and practices, teacher’s classroom, handling of lessons, children’s behaviour and class management, organizational training and orientation. It does not matter what type of person he is, the most important thing is the process, principles and philosophy of the environment. It is assumed that extroverts are more delinquent than introverts or ambiverted children since they are restless, boisterous, exert vigour and energy, yet personality development depends on the nature of socialization, training or orientation.

Remedial Measures for Adjusting Maladaptive Delinquents

Maladjustment is the opposite of adjustment and is a concept used to describe situation where individual efforts are put to satisfy their needs if society fails and so, they face the danger of frustration and disequilibrium in behavioural patterns. It is a phenomenon that operates mostly among children and adolescents. Adjustment on the other hand is the process of reaction to the demands and pressures of personal, social and academic environment imposed upon the individual. Adjustment may be positive or negative. If a person changes from good habit, to deviant attitude, it is a negative adjustment. When a child is

restless, aggressive, impudent, uncompromising, uncooperative and by the help of intervention measures he or she changes the bad attitude to good conduct, he or she is said to have undergone adjustment process and has therefore adjusted.

Psychotherapeutic measures that are adoptable for juvenile delinquents include individual and group counselling, family counselling, Rational emotive therapy, community-based counselling coupled with the use of media, modelling, shaping and imitation techniques and strategies. To change the attitude of delinquent, evidence from psychological experience have shown that attitude change depends on the credibility of the therapist or communicator; nature of appeals to the delinquent, organization of strategies to use for the appeal and relative commitment of the diligent client to his manifested attitude. These factors should be considered by therapists during intervention sessions (Mukherjee, 2002).

Conclusion

This paper discussed the concept of juvenile delinquency, its causes and probable solutions. Some of the causes discussed include biogenic, environmental, physiological and personal which natural physical attributes, inheritance and environmental (Nurture) as well as physiological factors were highlighted particularly, the family, the school, the peers and the media. Theories of juvenile delinquency, as well as the psychological and counselling implications were brought to lime light. This was proffered so as to serve as preventive and remediation measures against juvenile delinquency and to change the attitude of Nigerian youth who have the potentials for national development.

Recommendations

Based on this, the following recommendations are proffered: -

- Professional psychotherapists including counsellors, social workers and medical

personnel should be provided in all educational institutions in Nigeria to intervene in the psychosocial problems of children.

1. Parents'/Teachers' Association (P.T.A) should be used as a forum of enlightening parents on effective parenting of children, in terms of peer group and social network.
2. Parents and teachers should serve as stakeholders who are worthy of emulation in all their manifestations.
3. Children should be enrolled in schools and be taught vocational skills so that they can be economically independent and live sustainable life particular with loan scheme.
4. Award for good conduct should be introduced among students in various schools so as to motivate children to behave well wherever they may be.
5. Rules and regulations in various schools should be strictly adhered to and any child found wanting should face the wrath of the law. Cases of truancy, bullying, stealing, examination malpractices, sexual immorality, group or peer pressure will all be minimized drastically.

Reference

- Abubakar, A. L. (2018). *The Nature and causes of Juvenile delinquency in Nigeria*. Available at <https://abubakarlawankura.wordpress.com/2018/07/16The-nature-and-causes-of-juvenile-delinquency-in-nigeria/>
- A.H.C.E.A. (2000) *Teens and their parents in the 21st century: An examination of trend in teen behaviour and the role of Parent's involvement*. Author Publishers.
- Amojirionwu, S.A. (1974). *The delinquency pattern and treatment of adolescent misbaheviour*, Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis, Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Buzzelli, C.A. & Johnson, B. (2018). *The moral dimension of teaching*. Routledge Farmer.

- Carrie, H. Shandra & Dennis, P.H. (2012). Delinquency among adolescents with disabilities. *Child Indicators Research*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>.
- De Angelis, A. (2007) *Children*. Mc Graw – Hill
- Edward, D. (2017) *Eysenck theory of personality traits*. <https://study.com>academy>hans.cited17/06/2019>.
- Eno, P.N. (2000) Special education in Nigeria: Strategies for improvement. *The Exceptional Child*, 4,1 & 2,17 – 22.
- Farrinton, D. (2009) conduct disorder, aggression and delinquency. *Handbook of Adolescent Psychology*. NewYork: Wiley.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) *National Policy on Education Abuja*: Federal Government Press.
- George, I. (2007) *Issues of Juvenile delinquency*. <http://www.iiste.org/journals/datedJune18,2019>.
- Harris, K.M. (2009) the national longitudinal study of adolescent health, *Child Indicators Research*; 2007 – 2009. <https://www.ncbl.nim.govdated11/06/019>.
- Hetherington, E.M. & Kelly, J. (2002), *For better for worse. Divorce reconsidered*. Norton Publishers
- Ikene, T.N & Emodi, D.O (1987) incidence and causes of Truancy among secondary school students in Onitsha, Anambra State. *The Counsellor*, 7, 54-61.
- Kariku, A. (2016) *Causes of delinquency and ways to deal with it*. Retrieved from society and culture <http://www.enkivilage.com/category:society/culture> .
- Kay, W. (1970) *Moral development*. George Allen.
- Kreager, D. (2004) Strangers in the halls: Isolation and delinquency in school networks. *Social Forces*; 83, 351 – 390
- Loeber, R. & Farrington, D.P. (2001) *Child delinquents: Development, intervention and service needs*. SAGE Publications.
- Meadows, S.O (2007) Evidence of parallel pathways: gender similarity in the impact of social support on adolescent depression and delinquency. *Child Indicators Research*, 85, 1143-1167. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov.dated10/06/2019>.
- Mounts, N.S. (2002) Parental management of adolescent peer relationships in context: The role of parenting style. *Journal of Family Psychology*; 16, 60-63.
- Mukherjee, A. (2002) *Educational psychology*. S. Asekome & Co Publishers.
- Niyi, A. (2015) Factors responsible for juvenile delinquency in Nigeria: A case study of selected primary schools in Ikorodu, Lagos State, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences* 5(5), 79-99.
- Nwana, D.C. (1972) Major school offences in Nigeria. *Follow-up Study*; 1(2), 66-75
- Nwazuoke, I.A (2000) Professional preparation of teachers of exceptional children for inclusive contexts. *The Exceptional Child*; 4(1 & 2), 14-16.
- Pota, V. (2015) *Value the contributions teachers make to society*. Retrieved from URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14738/assr/.43.2611>
- Roth, J.& Brooks – Gunn, J. (2000). What do adolescents need for healthy development? Implications for youth policy. Social Policy Report. *Society for Research in Child Development* 14, 1-19.
- Stewart, S.D. (2005) How the birth of a child affects involvement with step children. *Journal of Marriage and the Family* 67, 645 – 469.
- Tayo, O.O. (2017) An appraisal of delinquent, behaviours among Secondary School Student in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Advance in Social Sciences Research Journal* 4 (3), 93-98.
- UNESCO (1990) *World Declaration on Education For All*. Retrieved from

[Http://Www.Unesco.Org/Education/Efa/Ed For All / Background Jointien](http://Www.Unesco.Org/Education/Efa/Ed%20For%20All%20Background%20Jointien%20declaration.Shtml) – declaration. Shtml.

UNESCO (1994) The *Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special needs Education*. Retrieved from

<http://www.unesco.org/education/pdf/SALAMA-E.PDF>.

UNICEF (2008) *Juvenile delinquency*.

[http://www.iiste.org/journals/datedJune 7,2019](http://www.iiste.org/journals/datedJune7,2019).